

Harnessing Traditional Knowledge in Sustainable Development of India and Brazil: A Comparative Exploration

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Abstract

Traditional knowledge refers to the knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities around the world. It tends to be collectively owned and takes the form of stories, songs, folklore, proverbs, cultural values, beliefs, rituals, community laws, local language and agricultural practices, including the development of plant species and animal breeds. Traditional knowledge is mainly of a practical nature, particularly in such fields as agriculture, fisheries, health, horticulture, forestry and environmental management in general. At present, unsustainable development has led to global warming, environmental destruction, conflict, poverty and hunger, vast inequalities and social instability. It is noteworthy that the traditional knowledge possessed by indigenous communities across the globe may be the 'key drivers' for poverty reduction, livelihood improvement and attaining sustainability of the given environment. Hence, this study aims to compare the use of traditional knowledge in achieving sustainable development by two foremost countries of the BRICS grouping, that is, Brazil and India. At present, Brazil is ranked 50th and India 112th amongst 166 countries as per the Sustainable Development Report 2023. Thus it becomes pertinent for both the countries to harness the diverse domain of indigenous knowledge in order to achieve a balance between economic growth and clean environment to meet the 2030 deadline for achieving Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: Traditional Knowledge, Sustainable Development, Knowledge Economy, Emerging Markets , Global South as Hub of Indigenous Knowledge, Economy vs Environment etc.

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1. Introduction

Traditional knowledge refers to the knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities around the world. Developed from experience gained over the centuries and adapted to the local culture and environment, traditional knowledge is transmitted orally from generation to generation. It tends to be collectively owned and takes the form of stories, songs, folklore, proverbs, cultural values, beliefs, rituals, community laws, local language and agricultural practices, including the development of plant species and animal breeds. It is mainly of a practical nature, particularly in such fields as agriculture, fisheries, health, horticulture, forestry and environmental management in general (CBD, 2007). Indigenous people possess, inhabit, or use a quarter of the world's surface area, conserving 80% of the world's multiculturalism that still exists (Lyon et al., 2017). They have essential inherited knowledge and capabilities for adapting to, mitigating, and minimizing the threats of climate change and calamities (Sahoo et al., 2022). At present, unsustainable development has led to global warming, environmental destruction, conflict, poverty and hunger, vast inequalities and social instability (UN, 2015). To solve this series of crises, sustainable development has to be undertaken that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland Commission Report, 1987). It is noteworthy that the world and the indigenous communities in it have a rich accumulation of knowledge based on their cultures, environments, social, political, and economic institutions, natural resources, etc. which may be according to (Boon & Hens, 2007), the 'key drivers' for poverty reduction, livelihood improvement, and attaining sustainability of the given environment (Indigenous Knowledge and Sustainability – Tribal Cultures of India, 2024).

1.1 Literature Review

Various studies have been carried out regarding comparison of economic growth and development in India and Brazil (Sirohi, 2017); creation of knowledge economy in both the countries (Pateo et al, 2020); sustainable development happening in them (Motta et al, 2021) and also on traditional knowledge regulation policies in the two countries (Eimer, 2019). But there exists a gap in linking all these parameters together- this becomes relevant in the present context where India and Brazil are both leading voices of Global South with emerging markets, both working to achieve sustainable development within 2030 and both of them having a rich tradition of indigenous knowledge. Hence, this study makes an effort to establish a coherent connection between traditional knowledge, economic growth and sustainable development through comparing the position of India and Brazil in using traditional knowledge for achieving sustainable development.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of the study have been conceived in the following manner:

- i) To assess the importance of traditional knowledge in modern times.
- ii) To examine how sustainable development can be used to bring a balance between environment and economy.
- iii) To analyse the relationship between traditional knowledge and sustainable development.
- iv) To scrutinize the progress made by two emerging economies of the world, i.e., India and Brazil in terms of achieving sustainable development goals.
- v) To study how India and Brazil are harnessing their traditional knowledge for sustainable development.

2. Methodology

The present study is based on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of secondary data as collected from different government portals, research articles published in journals and books, indices prepared by international organisations, newspaper reports and documentation of various initiatives undertaken by national and international NGOs.

Any economy of the world is mainly divided into three sectors, namely primary (eg. agriculture), secondary (eg. manufacturing and industry) and tertiary (eg. services like education and health). In this study, a predominant activity based on traditional knowledge in each of the three sectors for both the countries have been selected. In order to make the study diverse, in India, traditional knowledge as practiced in three states (namely, West Bengal, Arunachal Pradesh and Kerala) belonging to three different biogeographic zones (Plateau, Himalayan and coastal regions respectively) have been selected. In Brazil, activities based on traditional knowledge from three states (namely Sao Paulo, Rondônia, MatoGrosso) having three different biomes (Atlantic forest, Amazon rainforest and Pantanal wetland respectively) have been considered.

Here, a simple statistical method like percentage has been used to express the data.

3. Results

3.1 Economic Profile of India and Brazil: An Overview-

A brief glance at the IMF data on top 10 economies of the world in 2024 would show that India stands at the fifth position, with GDP of USD 4 trillion and Brazil at ninth position with GDP of USD 2 trillion. India and Brazil are both multi-trillion-dollar economies and members of the oft-cited BRICS countries along with Russia, South Africa, and China. Following are the key macroeconomic indicators of both the countries expressed in tabular form:

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Table 1: Macroeconomic Indicators, India

Fiscal Parameters	1980-90	1990-2000	2000-12	2012-22
GDP growth (annual %)	5.7	5.6	7.0	7.2
Agriculture, forestry and fishing, value added (annual % growth)	4.4	2.9	3.0	4.0
Industry, value added (annual % growth)	6.1	5.8	7.4	4.4
Services, etc., value added (annual % growth)	6.2	7.2	8.5	9.5
Gross savings (% of GDP)	21.1	24.1	31.8	30

Source: World Development Indicators (Online)

Table 2: Macroeconomic Indicators, Brazil

Fiscal Parameters	1980-90	1990-2000	2000-12	2012-22
GDP growth (annual %)	2.4	2.1	3.6	2.9
Agriculture, value added (annual % growth)	3.3	2.6	3.6	1.7
Industry, value added (annual % growth)	1.3	0.6	3.6	1.6
Services, etc., value added (annual % growth)	3.5a	2.8b	3.3	4.2
Gross savings (% of GDP)	19.8	15.5	16.3	16

Source: World Development Indicators (Online) (a: data from 1980 to 1989; b: data from 1992 to 2000)

While both are among the most-watched emerging markets, the Brazilian economy has attempted to combine the goals of redistribution and social equity with the goals of growth and productivity. India, on the other hand, has pursued a growth maximizing approach to development, while paying inadequate attention to the larger goals of human well-being. (Sirohi, 2017) This can be demonstrated by the GDP per capita of both countries (in USD thousand), while Brazil's value is 11.03, India's is staggering at 2.85. (IMF, 2024) Also, according to a report published by Oxfam International in 2023, the richest one per cent in India own more than 40 per cent of the country's total wealth. On the other side, Brazilian economy in recent times is facing issues like increasing economic inequality, hunger and malnutrition. On top of it, corruption scandals and crony capitalism are ruining the domestic economic sphere of Brazil. (Investopedia, 2023) During the previous government, there was an increase in levels of deforestation in Brazil (Dutra da Silva and Fearnside, 2022). At the same time, the government was heavily criticised for violation of human rights (Human Rights Watch, 2022), especially among indigenous and traditional populations. (Economics Observatory, 2023)

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3.2 Tracking the progress of Brazil and India on the path of Sustainable Development-

So the persistent issues of socio-economic inequalities, malnutrition, hunger, poverty etc., not only in both the countries but worldwide, call for a permanent solution, which can be best reflected by the Sustainable Development Agenda. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. At its heart are the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are an urgent call for action by all countries - developed and developing - in a global partnership. They recognize that ending poverty and other deprivations must go hand-in-hand with strategies that improve health and education, reduce inequality, and spur economic growth – all while tackling climate change and working to preserve our oceans and forests. (UN, 2015) The 17 SDGs are as follows:

- i) No Poverty
- ii) Zero Hunger
- iii) Good Health and Well-being
- iv) Quality Education
- v) Gender Equality
- vi) Clean Water and Sanitation
- vii) Affordable and Clean Energy
- viii) Decent Work and Economic Growth
- ix) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- x) Reduced Inequalities
- xi) Sustainable Cities and Communities
- xii) Responsible Consumption and Production
- xiii) Climate Action
- xiv) Life below Water
- xv) Life on Land
- xvi) Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions
- xvii) Partnerships for the Goals

3.2.1 Brazil's performance in achieving the SDGs:

The Sustainable Development Report 2023 shows that Brazil has ranked 50th among 166 countries, with a score of 73.69. Following image shows the level of progress achieved by the country in fulfilling the 17 SDGs.

SDG Dashboards and Trends

Click on a goal to view more information.

Figure 1: SDG Progress of Brazil

(Source: Sustainable Development Report, 2023)

The above image shows that Brazil is doing good on the affordable and clean energy front, while some hurdles still remain in achieving the goals of no poverty, clean water, industry and infrastructure, climate action and partnership for achieving SDGs. The country still needs to work more to solve issues of hunger, health, education, gender equality, creating sustainable cities and communities and in achieving employment and higher economic growth. Reducing inequality, improving life below water and on land, and creating strong institutions to maintain peace and justice are those areas in which it is still lagging far behind. Overall, it can be said that it is improving for 9 SDGS, i.e, Goals 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 11, 13 and 17. For 7 SDGS, i.e., Goals 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 16, the country is still at the same level, i.e., it is neither improving nor declining. The only SDG where Brazil’s performance is worsening is Goal 2 of achieving zero hunger.

3.2.2 India’s performance in achieving the SDGs:

The Sustainable Development Report 2023 shows that India has ranked 112th among 166 countries, with a score of 63.45. Following image shows the level of progress achieved by the country in fulfilling the 17 SDGs.

SDG Dashboards and Trends

Click on a goal to view more information.

Figure 2: SDG Progress of India

(Source: Sustainable Development Report, 2023)

The above image shows that India is doing good on the fronts of responsible consumption and production and also climate action, while some hurdles still remain in achieving the goal of quality education. The country still needs to work more to solve issues of no poverty, affordable clean energy, achieving employment and higher economic growth, reduced inequalities and partnership for achieving SDGs. Eliminating hunger, improving health and well-being of citizens, achieving gender equality, enhancing industry, innovation and infrastructural sectors, creating sustainable cities and communities, improving life below water and on land, and maintaining strong institutions to ensure peace and justice are those areas in which it is still lagging far behind. Overall, it can be said that it is improving for 11 SDGS, i.e., Goals 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 12, 14 and 17. For 4 SDGS, i.e., Goals 2, 11, 13 and 16, the country is still at the same level, i.e., it is neither improving nor declining. The 2 SDGs where India's performance is worsening are Goals 10 (reducing inequalities) and 15 (life on land).

3.3 Traditional Knowledge in achieving Sustainable Development Goals-

3.3.1 In India: I) Sericulture- Nowadays, agriculture is not confined within production and cultivation of traditional crops, farmers are also hinging on non-farm activities like sericulture, horticulture, animal husbandry etc. Therefore, sericulture represents an activity belonging to the **primary sector**.

Farmers have reared the tasar silkworm and processed silk cocoons into yarn and fabric in India since time immemorial. The insect species *Anthereae Mylitta* are reared on host plants such as

the *Terminalia sp.*, found abundantly in the tropical sub-humid forests covering the states of Jharkhand, Odisha, West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh and Telangana. *Tasar* silkworm-rearing is a traditional practice of the forest-dwelling communities, to supplement their livelihoods. Most of the silkworm rearers belong to indigenous communities (categorized as Scheduled Tribes in the Indian Constitution). Cocoons, made of silk filaments that have commercial value in the market, are harvested at the end of the silkworm-rearing cycle. According to The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI), India's annual silk demand is about 25,000 MT, whereas production is 17,000 MT. The gap is bridged with imports from China. So to meet the excess demand, *Tasar* cultivation has emerged as the most viable source of income with minimum investment, and high returns in tribal areas of Eastern and Central India (Jolly et al., 1975; Nath and Modak, 2022).

Case Study - Impact of Silkworm Cultivation in erstwhile Maoist-dominated JangalMahal area of West Bengal

Background: The JangalMahal area comprises the erstwhile areas of Manbhum, Mallabhum and Jhargram on the borders of Purulia, Bankura and Jhargram districts of West Bengal that fall in the south-eastern part of the Chota Nagpur Plateau. The region is characterized by a high concentration of tribal population, dense forest cover, and high level of landlessness of the peasants. The land in the western part is undulating, lateritic, and with low water-holding capacity. Agriculture in this part is mostly rain-fed; as a result, most of the lands are under mono-crop cultivation. The per capita income of the people living in this part is much lower than the average in the district. Overall, the level of vulnerability of households is very high, with respect to income, health, education and food security.

Gradual transformation of the area: *Tasar* sericulture by rearing Indian *Tasar* Silk Moth has long been an important traditional practice of a number of tribal communities that live there. Arjun and Asan trees, essential in this cultivation, are found in large numbers in this area. Consequently, these trees are keeping the fires of the hearth burning. State government, Central Silk Board and several NGOs like PRADAN (Professional Assistance for Development Action) have encouraged local inhabitants to pursue sericulture as an income-generating opportunity. The forest covers of Jangal Mahal, where Maoists first began their activities and where the Maoist menace held sway until a decade ago, have now become the breeding ground for silkworms. The farmers of Jangal Mahal are now in a well-to-do state through the cultivation of silkworms. Post the Maoist rampage, the wheels of prosperity have not stopped at spinning yards of silk only but have led to the construction of bridges in and around the villages, at the outskirts of the previously Maoist-infested forests. These bursts of development have given an impetus to the zeal of the peasants engaged in the cultivation of silkworms, encompassing more and more families into the silken net. With government aid, the villagers have used their own land to

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construct seed production units for the production of their own quality seed, thus generating employment in the villages. The ‘tasar cocoons’ thus prepared here are sent by truck to the silk mills of Bankura’s Bishnupur, Purulia’s Raghunathpur as well as to the silk mills of Odisha. Silk threads produced in these mills are utilized in making sarees, kurtis and other clothes. Earlier, the silk cultivators had to purchase tasar eggs from the government Sericulture Department; and as they now produce the tasar eggs themselves, the profit margins have increased. (PRADAN, 2018)

II) MSME- In India, the term ‘MSME’ refers to micro, small and medium enterprises, with an annual turnover of not more than Rs. 5 crore, Rs. 50 crore and Rs. 250 crore respectively. This belongs to the **secondary sector** of the economy. The importance of the MSME sector lies in the fact that it is contributing about 33% to India’s GDP and thus is playing a pivotal role in India’s growth story. Thus for bringing about innovation in India’s MSME sector, it becomes essential to harness the rich traditional knowledge possessed by indigenous people.

Case Study - Monpa- A Tribal Textile of Arunachal Pradesh

Overview of tribal textile tradition in Arunachal: Textile occupies a prominent place in the life of human beings from the beginning of civilization. Topographical variations, mineral resources, water, flora, and fauna are all contributory factors to the emergence of a distinct textile heritage of India. Traditional Indian textiles are deeply rooted in the rural background, natural elements, and folk culture. (RaiVerman, 2022) The northeastern area of India is a compelling cultural patchwork rich in tradition and wildlife. The linguistic variety, as well as different traditions and heritage, are represented in handloom goods from the Northeast. Northeast handloom goods have strong, historic roots in Arunachal Pradesh’s exceptional artistry. Arunachal Pradesh, which literally means “land of dawn-lit mountains,” is India’s easternmost state. The state is home to 26 major tribes and sub-tribes, with each tribe having its own set of traditions and customs. Arunachal Pradesh’s goods are known across the world for their unique patterns and inherent organic materials utilized in the weaving of diverse garments. Colors and patterns have profound importance for several Arunachal Pradesh tribes. In most tribal societies, the decorative stripe signifies the particular tribe - and sometimes even the status of the wearer in the tribe.

Monpa textile tradition: The Monpas are one of the foremost Himalayan tribes inhabiting the state of Arunachal Pradesh. They have been weaving cloth to meet their requirements since time immemorial. Weaving in their society is done almost exclusively by women. Girls are trained in the art of weaving from a very early age. In a family where there is no weaver, either a weaver is engaged by family to weave cloth whenever necessary on payment basis or they buy woven clothes from them. (Google Arts and Culture, 2024)

The basic raw materials used by them in weaving are wool and cotton yarn. They shear their sheep and do the washing, combing, spinning and weaving. Cotton yarn is imported from the plains of woolens which meet their essential requirement of clothing.

Figure 3: Monpa Women's Traditional Attire

While their geographical distribution is reflected in their varying dialects, across the tribe's subgroups, Monpa attire is almost always in a single colour: maroon. It is the colour of the *shinka*, the sleeveless pleated *eri* silk chemise the tribe's women wear. The *todung* (jacket) and the *tengnakema* (square cloth tied around the waist), are also a shade of maroon. While the men's jacket (*khanjar*) can be black, the summer vest (*aliphodung*), is again maroon—a warm colour to match the cold environs. (The Voice of Fashion, 2024) Horses, yak, the sun, mountains, riders, are some of the motifs that are part of its signature. This marvelous handloom tradition has also been given the GI (Geographical Indication) tag. (Geographical Indications Registry, 2023)

III) Ethnomedicine- Medical and healthcare services belong to the **tertiary sector** of an economy. In most traditional cultures, health equates physical, mental, social, spiritual and ecological balance. According to the traditional Ayurveda system of medicine, the outside world and the living being share all the elements in common; the being is a miniature representation of the universe; and, equilibrium is essential for health and well-being. Thus health is considered an interactive outcome of personal attributes, habitual experiences and interaction with the environment, whereas well-being can relate to multiple factors such as material comfort, health, freedom of choice and action, social support systems and security. Today, there is an increasing recognition of the social and ecological dimensions and determinants of health. Traditional medicine forms a central health seeking arena for a large part of the world population in developing countries (WHO, 2002). Ethnomedicine is highly dependent on ecosystems for

providing services, such as natural medicinal resources and nutritional sources. It also depends on cultural or recreational services insofar as nature, the environment and their attributes have cultural, religious and symbolic value in determining health and promoting healing.

Case Study - Traditional medicine in public health care of Kerala

Overview of prevailing healthcare system in Kerala: Kerala has a unique health care model of high health status at low per capita expenditure. The state has also achieved a relatively high human development index. Studies on the high health status of the state suggest a strong relationship between health status and cultural knowledge traditions. In the field of health, the state provides a unique example of how cultural traditions can interact with modernity in a complex way. The system has promoted positive attitudes to healthcare, diet, personal hygiene and sanitation, which have also been conducive to the acceptance of more modern approaches. Cultural elements that perceive health as a holistic system relating to physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual dimensions and that prescribe elaborate procedures for achieving total well-being have been well integrated (Gunatilleke, 1984; Payyappallimana, 2010).

Susceptibility of Kerala's population to waterborne diseases: To illustrate an aspect of such integration, an example of contemporary medicated drinking water practice is presented here. Water-related diseases form up to 80% of public health problems in India. According to Census 2011, among the states, Kerala has the lowest access to potable drinking water: rural – 28.3% and urban – 39.4%. A large percentage of households use drinking water from their own water sources such as open wells (Kunhikannan & Aravindan, 2000), which are considered susceptible to contamination. In the state, latrines are made with septic tanks (35% rural, 57% urban) and pour flush pit (29.3% rural, 25.5% urban), representing the highest rates in India. Kerala is the most densely populated state in India with 860 persons per km². (Census 2011)The normal annual rainfall of Kerala is 3,107 mm (the India national average is 1,197 mm) with an average 120-140 rainy days in a year. The state has 44 rivers and a large number of water bodies, making it highly susceptible to waterborne diseases. Waterborne vector diseases like dengue fever, malaria and chikungunya are on the rise due to urbanization and deteriorating environmental conditions. According to the National Sample Survey, the perception of an increase in mosquito population is reported high in Kerala. This shows the relatively low quality of water bodies in the state. However, the state has controlled cholera, diarrhoea, hepatitis and other waterborne diseases that spread through consumption of contaminated water (Kunhikannan & Aravindan, 2000).

Traditional knowledge of consuming boiled water: According to Kerala Water Authority (KWA), well water is the major source of drinking water in Kerala and around 90% of wells in Kerala are polluted by sewage. Presence of coliform bacteria was found in three out of four cases

in the rural areas of Thiruvananthapuram (capital city of Kerala), though no major health problems are reported in these areas. The state environment report says that “This may be attributed to the practice of boiling water before drinking. Boiling water before drinking is a time-tested method of water purification, but this tradition is being gradually replaced by the increasing use of bottled water.” The local population has developed some natural adaptations to an environment filled with water bodies and with a high prevalence of waterborne diseases. It is reported that the state has the highest percentage of households boiling drinking water in rural areas- 92.3% and in urban areas 82.14%. (Binu et al, 2021) This practice is related to the traditional culture of Kerala of consuming medicated boiled water. This traditional knowledge has continued as a popular social tradition for several generations even in the context of modernization.

3.3.2 In Brazil: I) Agriculture- Brazil is the most biodiverse country in the world, with more than 46,578 native plant species identified (Flora do Brasil 2020) and thousands of traditional communities who have known and managed biodiversity and landscapes for centuries, or even thousands of years. The indigenous systems of agricultural and forest management in Brazilian forests are characterized by a deep knowledge of ecological processes, biodiversity, and the use and management of fire. (Schmidt et al, 2021) Agriculture, belonging to the **primary sector**, has been historically one of the principal bases of Brazil's economy

Case Study-Traditional agricultural system of Quilombola Community

Overview of the Quilombos: The Atlantic Forest is one of the most biodiverse and threatened biomes on the planet. Most of its remnants are located in the Ribeira Valley, where most of the Sao Paulo state's quilombola population (or quilombos) is located. The quilombos of the valley arose from villages formed by abandoned, runaway and freed slaves who have been occupying the valley since the beginning of European colonization in the region in the sixteenth century. The main subsistence strategy these populations have developed is slash-and-burn agriculture (coivara), a system capable of proffering great heterogeneity to the forest landscape. (Munari, 2010)

Legacy of Coivara: Coivara is a type of swidden cultivation practiced by traditional populations in tropical forests, based on rotating farming areas, thereby combining production with conservation. In swidden cultivation, small areas of forest (between 0.5 and 1 ha) are slashed and burned to be cultivated for short intervals of time (approximately 3–5 years). After the cultivation period, the area is abandoned for the land to “rest” (or fallow) for about 15 years, sufficient for the woody vegetation to become dominant (Conklin 1961). In this sense, swidden cultivation involves a complex spatial and temporal management of the landscape. As a consequence of the rotational nature of the system, the landscape is a mosaic formed by fallows and secondary forests of different ages of regeneration, in addition to farms currently in use.

While it is often considered controversial and requires adaptations in times of climate change, partial and controlled burning of the land helps boost the potassium, calcium and magnesium levels in the soil, as well as the accumulation of organic carbon, which is a fertilizer for tropical forests soils that are often poor in nutrients.

The form of TQAS (Traditional Quilombola Agricultural System) practiced in the Ribeira Valley includes observing the phases of the moon to start planting. They believe that if the seeds are planted during the waning moon, there won't be pests later. Thus, they don't use any pesticides and grow crops naturally. (Mongabay, 2022)

II) Social Forestry-Brazil is a country with floral megadiversity, possessing six ecological domains, namely, Amazonian forest, Caatinga, Pampas, Cerrado, Atlantic Forest, and the Pantanal. It has 59.3% area under forest. (FAO, 2021) Brazil's primary wood-using industries include charcoal based cement, zinc, iron and steel-making companies, pulp and paper mills, composite and hardboard plants, veneer and plywood mills, wood preservation plants, and

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sawmills. Important secondary forest industries produce furniture, windows, doors, wooden houses, pallets and other products. (Couto and Dube, 2001) According to the national report of forest products (IBGE 2019), the products related to silviculture (i.e., exploitation of forest plantations) and timber extractivism (i.e., the harvesting of timber from natural resources) between 2016 and 2019 provided an average value of about R\$ 20.6 billion. In order to promote sustainable forest development by reconciling the use of natural resources with the protection of ecosystems supporting economic and social initiatives by populations that live and depend on forests, social forestry becomes important. Hence, social forestry boosts **secondary sector** in Brazil to a large extent.

Case Study- Reforestation of the Amazon Rainforest in Rondônia

Background: Among the six biomes, the Amazon is particularly important, being the largest biome in Brazil, covering 49% of the country area. Rondônia, a state located in central-western part of Brazil, used to be home to over 200,000 km² of rainforest, but has become one of the most deforested places in the Amazon. This is because all major tropical forests—including the Amazon, has been under human pressure, to make way for human food production, including livestock and crops. Although deforestation meets some human needs, it also has profound, sometimes devastating, consequences, including social conflict, extinction of plants and animals, and climate change—challenges that affect the whole world. (NASA, 2024) While Amazonian deforestation has global consequences, few people are more affected than the over 400 Indigenous communities who have called the Amazon home for centuries. (CSIS, 2020)

Contribution of indigenous communities in reforestation: As the frontline against forest loss, indigenous peoples and local communities are critical contributors to global goals for biodiversity protection and climate action. One-third of the Amazon's total carbon stocks are

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located in indigenous territories. So far they have been well protected- indigenous territories experienced just 0.1% net carbon loss from 2003 to 2016, the lowest rate anywhere in the Amazon. (Forest Trends) Indigenous communities of the Brazilian Amazon like Aikanã, Gavião, Sabanê, Suruí, Tupari and Zoró have founded the Amazonian Bioeconomic Seed Network in mid-2021. Such a network of seed collectors is a foundational part of the ecological restoration chain and will play an essential role in enabling Brazil to reach its goal of restoring 12.5 million hectares of native vegetation by 2030, including 4.8 million hectares in the Amazon.

The role of a seed collector is to monitor the flowering- i.e., to see if the flower will bloom, open, turn into fruit, and if the fruit will ripen. Seeds of native Amazon plant species like Angelim (*Diniziaexcelsa*), Cashew (*Anacardiumoccidentale*), Tamboril (*Enterolobium maximum*), Ipê (*Handroanthus sp.*) etc. are collected by them, which are planted to restore the local flora.

There are different techniques for processing the seeds. Collectors left Caroba (*Jacaranda brasiliiana*) seeds to dry out in the sun, which allows them to remove the tip of the fruit and cut it open with a machete. With seeds from the Garapa (*Apuleialeiocarpa*), a tree that can grow to a height of 40 meters (130 feet) in the Amazon, they rubbed them in a sieve with a flip-flop to separate the small seeds, using a brush cutter to speed up the process. To extract the seeds of the jatobás-do-cerrado (*Hymenaeastigonocarpa*), they placed them on a tarpaulin on firm ground and drove over them with a car to break them up. The different seeds were then divided into batches and taken to the seed houses, where they were stored in a cool, dark, dry and controlled environment. It is important that the seed is healthy, clean, that it is not mixed with other species, and that it doesn't have fungus, beetles or borers.

Brazilian law allows logging for economic activities on one fifth of the total area of private lands in the Amazon region—any percentage higher than that is illegal, and landowners are required to restore such vegetation. The collected seeds can be sold, especially to farmers and organizations willing to comply with the law. Seed collectors receive their payments based on the number of quality seeds collected.

The success of the network can be attributed to a number of factors:-

- i) appreciation of the different Indigenous cultures of those involved
- ii) partnership with the InstitutoSocioambiental (ISA), an advocacy group, which has provided technical training to collectors and conducted workshops on seed quality and management
- iii) use of the *muvuca* method, in which a mix of seeds from up to 80 species is sown directly into the soil.

In 2017, the Brazilian government drew up its National Plan for the Recovery of Native Vegetation, which includes the provision of technical training, “structured and relevant” forest extension, and the improvement of the seed and sapling production chain. The national plan of action also outlined market stimulus and financial mechanism development to incentivize the recovery of native vegetation. (Mongabay, 2023) Thus, governmental efforts, together with the initiatives of local communities, would help in restoration of Amazon rainforest in the state of Rondônia.

III) Ethnopharmacology-It is a part of the **tertiary sector** of Brazil’s economy. The country also possesses notable cultural diversity as it hosts diverse traditional communities in its territories, namely, the Indians descents (Amerindians), African descents, and the white Europeans. So, Brazil has a rich history of different traditions of ethnopharmacology practiced in different parts of the country.

Case Study- Ethnopharmacology of medicinal plants in the state of Mato Grosso

Overview of the Pantanal ecosystem found in Mato Grosso: Pantanal is one of the six important ecological domains found in Brazil. The Pantanal is distinguishably the largest wetland ecosystem of the world, according to the classification by UNESCO World Heritage Center (Biosphere Reserve). The vegetation is a mosaic consisting of species of the Amazonian rainforest, Cerrado, Atlantic forest, and Bolivian Chaco, adapted to special conditions, where there is alternation of both high humidity and pronounced dryness during a year. Because of the fact that the Pantanal communities are relatively isolated, they have developed private lives that involve much reliance on profound knowledge of the biological cycles, utilization of natural resources, and traditional technology heritage. The presence in the Pantanal of the traditional populations that use medicinal plants for basic health care makes this region an important field for ethnobotanical and ethnopharmacological studies. (Bieski et al, 2012) The Mato Grosso state, located in Central-West Brazil, hosts the Pantanal ecosystem.

Map of the Pantanal ecoregion

Location of Mato Grosso (in red) in Brazil

Use of medicinal plants by rural communities: Due to the low level of knowledge of traditional medicine in national capitals, ethnobotanical surveys in Brazil primarily prefer to evaluate small communities or rural hometowns, whose population having knowledge and practical experience with traditional medicine are proportionately higher (between 80 and 100%) (Vendruscolo and Mentz, 2006). The high percentage of folk knowledge of medicinal plants identified in Brazil may be due to factors such as lower influence of the contemporary urban lifestyle and the strength of cultural traditions in the rural communities (Upadhyay et al, 2010). In fact, with the process of industrialization and migration to the cities, a significant part of traditional culture is maintained more in the communities farther from the metropolis via oral transmission of the knowledge of CAM (complementary and alternative medicine) and family traditions. In Brazil, as in other countries, rural communities have developed knowledge about the medicinal and therapeutic properties of natural resources and have contributed to the maintenance and transmission of the ethnopharmacological knowledge within the communities. (Bieski et al, 2012)

A study conducted in 2012 by Bieski et al showed that local healers from rural communities in MatoGrosso like Chumbo, Bahia de Campo, Agroana etc. documented use of high number of taxa (285 genera, 376 species and 102 families) as medicinal plants. The most representative plant families were Fabaceae (10.2%), Asteraceae (7.82%) and Lamiaceae (4.89%). Those plants were mostly used for the treatment of pain and inflammation (10.8%), kidney disease (7.6%) and wound healing (6.8%). Following is the table showing species of relatively higher importance in terms of medicinal use:

Table 3: Species with the highest values of relative importance

Family	Species	Application
Apocynaceae	<i>Himatanthusobovatus</i>	anemia, wound healing, cholesterol, blood cleanser, pain, nose bleeding, hypertension, uterine inflammation, labyrinthitis, muscle relaxant, worms, vitiligo and pneumonia
Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	anxiety, flu, tachycardia, kidney infection, cramps, discharge, diarrhea, pain, uterine inflammation, labyrinthitis, snakebite and pneumonia
Asteraceae	<i>Solidagomicroglossa</i>	wound healing, blood cleanser, pain, bone fractures, hypertension, uterine inflammation, muscle relaxant, kidney infection and worms
Loganiaceae	<i>Strychnospseudoquina</i>	anemia, wound healing, cholesterol, blood cleanser, stomach pain, bone fractures, flu, uterine inflammation, pneumonia, muscle relaxant, cough, ulcer and worms
Moraceae	<i>Dorsteniabrasiliensis</i>	wound healing, colic, tooth ache, blood cleanser, dysentery, pain, flu, laxative, menstruation, pneumonia, postpartum relapse and kidney infection

Source: Bieski et al, 2012

Of the abovementioned plant species, *Himatanthusobovatus* has antibiotic properties. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* contains polyphenol acids, flavonoids, and anthocyanins- which may act as antioxidants or through other mechanisms, may contribute to cardioprotective activity. *Solidagomicroglossa* has antimicrobial properties. *Strychnospseudoquina* has gastroprotective effect due to presence of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory agents. *Dorsteniabrasiliensis* contains Dorstenic acid A and B (triterpenoids), which have shown mild cytotoxicity against leukemia cells. (Bieski et al, 2012)

4. Discussion

The abovementioned six activities based on traditional knowledge have a profound impact on the lives of communities practicing them, which can be mentioned as follows:

- i) **Sericulture as a means of women empowerment:** Women were previously barred from taking part in silkworm rearing; traditionally only male members of tribal households (including children) reared silkworms in forests. However, women's entry into the sector has proved necessary to break a significant barrier towards equal participation of women in supporting livelihoods and to reinvigorate a sector in distress. Women producers have set up

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a Producers' Organisation (PO) named 'JangalMahalMahila Tasar Chasir Dal Community Trust', and trains members in governance and management of POs. Building and strengthening POs to organize production and marketing systems involves capacity building to manage the entire seed vertical (nucleus seed, basic seed and commercial seed) for the supply of high-quality eggs, aggregating produce and creating linkages with fairer markets. The initiative to revive the silk value chain with women at the helm has created an opportunity for women to demonstrate that they have the discipline and punctuality required in silkworm rearing and tasar seed production, in addition to the capacity to maintain the required hygienic conditions in the rearing field and seed production, essential for quality production of eggs and enhancement of productivity. The women have also gained valuable financial management experience through the POs. Moreover, through their four-year-long endeavour, they have capitalized and demonstrated an earning of nearly Rs. 68,000 per family from tasar sericulture over the period. At the household level, changes have taken place in gender roles. Tasar rearing has thus promoted women's empowerment. (PRADAN, 2018)

- ii) **Economic Prospect of tribal textiles in Arunachal:** In Arunachal Pradesh more than 1 Lakh weavers exist as per the Handloom Census is concerned. Weaving activity is only second to agriculture activities in the state. The Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) of Arunachal Pradesh for 2023-24 (at current prices) is projected to be Rs 37,870 crore. It stands among the lowest five states in India in terms of GSDP value. Therefore, the state needs to focus on training the weavers, creating public awareness about various handloom products belonging to different tribes and marketing them. This would boost not only the state's economic growth but also raise the standard of living of tribal people and contribute to women empowerment (as mostly girls are involved in weaving the fabrics). (North East GIS, 2023)
- iii) **Importance of ethnomedicine:** Such prescriptions have roots in the regional ancient Ayurvedic medical text books which recommend enhancing water quality by boiling it with several locally grown medicinal plants. There are two likely benefits of this practice: microbe-free boiled water together with the physiological and clinical benefits of medicinal substances used in the boiling process. According to the local traditional understanding most systemic diseases are caused by faulty metabolic processes: drinking water has a strong effect on mitigating such effects both in states of health and illness. Based on this, specific preparations are made for preventive and curative purposes. According to Moni Nag (1989), the "Kerala tradition of drinking water that has been boiled with cumin seeds (jeerampani) and the water remaining after rice has been boiled (kanji) may have contributed toward lower morbidity and mortality." Today medicated water forms an essential component even in restaurants and public functions, which shows good market integration and livelihood benefits with several small enterprises producing and marketing such products supported by

the Kerala Khadi and Village Industries Board and similar organizations. (Payyappallimana et al, 2010) This case presents the inherent linkage between cultural knowledge and environment and how biological and cultural precepts interrelate to form adaptations to the local environment.

- iv) **Outcomes of TQAS- Genetic diversity and food security:** A total of 83 varieties belonging to 42 species, annual and perennial, are cultivated by them. (Gonsalves et al, 2022) Women have a direct connection to germplasm conservation, due to their strong influence over which material will or will not remain in the homegardens and crop fields, depending on dietary preferences. Most farmers cultivate for self-consumption and also share with other families through donations. Some crops are also primarily intended for sale, such as bananas (*Musa acuminata*). In addition to the annual species, perennial species, such as orange (*Citrus sinensis*) and grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*), and native semi-perennial species, such as passion fruit (*Passiflora edulis*) were also observed. Considering the nutritional value of locally grown agrobiodiversity, the diversity of carbohydrates and proteins in their diet are provided by crops such as pea (*Pisum sativum*), fava bean (*Vicia faba*), sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*), and corn (*Zea mays*). Other species are also important due to the richness of cultivated varieties, such as beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea*), bananas, sweet manioc (*Manihot esculenta*), and sweet potatoes. It is known that plant conservation and the use of inter and intraspecific genetic diversity in food are sustainable alternatives against hunger and malnutrition (Peroni and Hanazaki 2002; Pingali et al. 2005). In the study of Gonsalves et al (2022), it was found that diversification of food production and the amount of food produced, influenced lower food vulnerability among the families of the community. Thus, farmers who manage more species and local varieties contribute to a lower vulnerability of food insecurity, especially among their relatives. To conserve this unique cultivation system, the TQAS of the Ribeira Valley was declared part of Brazil's intangible cultural heritage in 2018. (Mongabay, 2022)
- v) **Seed Collection as a tool of women empowerment:** Collectors working with the Amazonian Bioeconomic Seed Network are mostly women. As well as serving as the raw material for restoring degraded areas, seeds are also used in the making of jewellery, a new source of income for indigenous women in eight territories within Rondônia. They have also established an online store to sell jewellery made with seeds all over Brazil. (Mongabay, 2023)
- vi) **Prospects of Ethnopharmacology:** The practice of traditional medicinal plant species to treat diseases itself represents an important strategy for preservation of local culture and sustenance of popular knowledge of CAM in the local systems of health care and environmental education. Despite the fact that modern medicine, on the basis of the complex pharmaceutical industry, is well developed in most parts of the world, the World Health Organization (WHO), through its Traditional Medicine Program, recommends its Member

States to formulate and develop policies for the use of CAM in their national health care programmes. (Bieski et al, 2012)

4.1 Challenges Remain-

4.1.1 Common problems regarding traditional knowledge: While traditional knowledge (TK) is being used in different sectors of economic activities by the indigenous communities throughout the world, certain obstacles regarding integration of traditional knowledge in sustainable development still persist even today- which are common to both India and Brazil. (Payyappallimana, 2010)

I. Comparatively inferior view regarding TK: Jenkins (2000) says that modernization has dramatically devalued traditions by universalizing norms of action, value generation and individualized patterns of socialization. In the process, tradition in general and TK in particular have been relegated to the sidelines as a scarce, non-renewable resource and an impediment to progress (Jenkins, 2000). Also, alternate worldviews get marginalized, especially due to modernity's characterization of history as being linear and evolutionary. This leads to a 'critical and skeptical judgment' of older knowledge (Couze & Featherstone, 2006).

II. Focus on economic utility rather than cultural context: In the efforts to achieve 'development,' emphasis has been placed on economic growth. In the same vein, the role of culture or TK in contemporary societies has been examined through the lens of relevance to commercial activity. According to Jenkins (2000) "Social analysis has been largely driven by rational behaviour models, which abstract economic action from its historical contexts." For example, cultural knowledge, artifacts or art forms are seen as vehicles for economic empowerment with less focus on their contextual nature and relevance to the communities.

III. Efforts more directed towards preservation than finding contemporary utility of TK: Prevailing view of TK as antiquated and non-dynamic relegates it to a status of a commodity that should be documented and preserved. The discourse has been dominated by the protection of intellectual property rights while neglecting efforts to strengthen the social and cultural processes of continuity and contemporary utility of such knowledge. Whereas documentation and preservation of TK (being on the verge of extinction) are needs of the hour, promotion of contemporarily relevant TK and encouraging continued creativity and dynamism are vital as well.

4.1.2 Comparison between TK policies in India and Brazil: TK plays an important role for indigenous groups in both countries; however, it is also sought by domestic researchers and the transnational life sciences industry. Whereas Brazilian indigenous communities (Índios) have been able to effectively defend at least a legal recognition of their self-determination rights, the

virtually identical demands of indigenous (Adivasi) communities in India have remained nearly neglected. These differences are all the more puzzling considering that the relative proportion of Adivasis in Indian society (8.6%) is far higher than that of Índios in Brazil (0.2%). (Eimer, 2019)

I. TK Policies in Brazil: Brazil has provided utmost importance to **consent of indigenous communities** with regards to use of traditional knowledge. Self-determination rights of indigenous were strengthened by the procedural rules developed by the Ministry of Environment between 2003-08, which ensured that TK could only be accessed if indigenous communities agreed to its disclosure. Indigenous representatives in Brazil have cooperated with a broad range of other groups such as the Quilombólas, rubber-tappers, Ribeirinhos (riparian communities in the Amazon) etc. to present themselves as ‘guardians of nature’ to justify their demands for the respect of their customary rules with regard to TK.

Indigenous spokespersons, together with Brazilian diplomats, have demanded an amendment of international intellectual property law- that would obligate transnational pharmaceutical firms to document the recognition of indigenous rights in patent applications in the jurisdictions of industrialised countries. However, despite the support of many developing countries, Brazilian diplomats have not been able to overcome the resistance of the majority of industrialised countries, who favour the interests of their domestic pharmaceutical industries. (Eimer, 2019)

II. TK Policies in India: Many Indians associate self-determination with the threat of secession, which is highly sensitive because of the country’s experiences during the partition period and the ongoing border disputes. Against this background, Adivasi spokespersons are not able to steer the Indian debate on TK towards their own interests. Both the National Biodiversity Act (2002) and the Biodiversity Rules (2004, amended in 2014) require the consent of governmental authorities; however, the Adivasi and other local communities have no statutory ‘right to say no’ to the access of their knowledge.⁹⁴ While the regulations stipulate the establishment of local biodiversity management committees (BMCs) to ensure the participation of indigenous actors, these bodies often do not exist on the ground.

However, Indian regulations place much more emphasis on the **prevention of bio-piracy**. Transnational firms are at least legally subjected to strict authorisation procedures to prevent unremunerated access to TK. Even more important is the establishment of the Indian Traditional Knowledge Digital Library (TKDL), which documents both the written medicinal knowledge of the Vedas and the TK of indigenous communities. Whereas access to the database is narrowly restricted for non-Indian researchers, its content is used to contest patent applications in industrialised countries on the basis of prior (Indian) knowledge and to support the research projects of the Indian pharmaceutical industry. (Eimer, 2019)

5. Conclusion

To prepare the world for undertaking sustainable development, implementing Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) becomes important. ESD is a process of learning that aims to empower individuals and communities to make informed decisions and take responsible actions for environmental, social, and economic sustainability. This would solve the problem of integrating TK in sustainable development. Also, both consent and prevention of biopiracy are important parameters with regards to use of TK. Both these parameters should be taken into account while framing policies on use on TK by India as well as Brazil. As per the Global Innovation Index 2023, India ranked 40th whereas Brazil had a rank of 49 amongst 132 countries. (WIPO, 2023) To bolster their position as leading knowledge economies of the Global South, India and Brazil has to cooperate for integrating use of traditional knowledge in every sector of the economy to develop in a sustainable manner.

5.1 Limitation of Study

All the data collected are secondary in nature.

5.2 Avenues for further research

Research can be conducted in following areas:

- i) Comparison of traditional knowledge in sustainable development amongst all the five BRICS countries, i.e., Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa
- ii) Quantification of indigenous economy so as to highlight the share of tribal economy in India's GDP or in a state's GSDP
- iii) Use of traditional arts and crafts practiced by Brazilian communities to foster small-scale industries

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